

Implementation of Database models with SQL Queries for a typical mobile application using c#

(Benchmarking to a novel mobile application)

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Abstract- In recent days, the smartphone applications have been evolved tremendously in the field of Information Technology. Most of the social networks now become mobile based so as the number of mobile users increases rapidly. The end user requirement is a vital role in making mobile applications. In mobile communication perspective views, every end user is a customer and everyone is identified themselves by a unique mobile number. In another perspective view, every end user needs more than a task, it is being communicated to some other end user who able to provide the exact service or task to that end user. This paper illustrates some database management model to identify the peoples or end users based on their jobs, services, social services, professional standings, and liable partners to government or private sector companies. The mobile uses a unique mobile number to identify a person. The question is, what are the tasks a mobile user wanted? And how it is being communicated to others who can offer the same task, and how it is being made by another end user. The SQL statements will be effectively implemented in this research paper. Every mobile user will be getting a benefit when this is executed between the mobile users. In this approach, the uniqueness of the number identification changes to some attributes, roles or services of the users. This attributes may be their services, performances, professions and professional standings. Based on these attributes, the values of table tuples, columns and data types will be designed. This database model will be very useful for storing and retrieving the enormous contact information among the mobile users in all the Personal Computers also.

Keywords— data models; knowledge representation; mobile applications; sql applications; query language practices

I. Introduction

In recent days, mobile applications have been evolved tremendously. It includes a lot of graphical applications, social networking related applications, and especially web applications. ^[1] The number of mobile user increases as that an average session is 37 % longer in the Home-context than in the Office-context. These applications may be developed either based on single customer requirement or based on company's requirement. Consider a customer, who is having mobile phone with its unique mobile number. Who are all know his mobile number, those people only can get connected with this customer. If this customer wants to give mobile number to others, then it is possible to create a communication between these two people. Every individual mobile user can get so

many services from other customers by addressing them based on their service. Consider a mobile user regularly used to go to the office by bike, this mobile user wants to give 'pick up and drop' service to any other mobile user. ^[2] For this, this mobile user has to register in a database mentioning that this user is ready to offer the above said service to any other mobile user at particular time. Making mobile users to communicate or address themselves based on their different choices is the main purpose. It may be service oriented or may be fully customer oriented. For example, consider a customer, who wants to withdraw some amount from ATM or bank. But, the customer has to achieve this quickly. By using this application, bank can depute one officer to work in 24 hours' time, that officer should be authorized by the particular branch of that bank. Now, that customer is ready to ask service through the particular branch by searching the queries with the following key words 'banking service', 'branch name' and 'withdraw'. Then these keywords give the mobile number of the particular officer to the customer. Customer can make a call to him, then the officer will finish the need of the customer.

Consider another customer, this mobile user wants to give two wheeler 'pickup' service between particular points. The customer has to register in a particular category which is related to a certain service. While other customer needs the same service, this data will be displayed to that particular customer. So the communication will be created between the two customers based on their requirements. The registered data is purely taken from a database which was created earlier, but also available in the web. This paper aims to create such applications in mobiles so that the dimensions of addressing the mobile users will become different. If a person or mobile user want to share something more relevant things to others, it is restricted to their wish anyway. It is really an optional choice on both either in getting service or in offering service. This paper illustrates some data models, how they can be classified, what are the queries used and simple case studies. In later part, this paper demonstrates some issues and its causes to the customer. This is fully a customer oriented applications so every customer has to take responsibilities to prevent the malfunctioning of the application. Very good customer behaviour should be expected, the level of satisfactory is fully depends upon the service given by individual customer. The personal details verification can be done by the network provider, and network provider only can say that this is a valid

customer, but while getting or offering service, the customer has to take necessary steps to avoid the malfunctioning. The main purpose of this application, provide the contact number of the specified people to the required people.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Queries to select a mobile user to offer a service

In all search based applications, SQL can be used well as it deals with database and queries. There are many categories in which all the customer can seek service in the database [3]. The following operations can be involved with that: storage, transactions, caching and information indexing. Personal offer, public offer, private offer, official offer call. Primarily, a customer has to identify the service category in which the particular service is available in the database. Knowing the suitable partner is simply better than knowing the partner. A student wants a teacher for mathematics tuition. Usually the student has to register in any website which provides very good information about the teacher, their location and other options also. But, it is a formal procedure, where the registered teachers list only will be shown in that particular web. So it cannot be refined with the student's need and requirement. Because, consider sometime due to lack of money, some very good teachers might not registered in that particular website, also those teachers are boarding very near to that student who needs tuition immediately. In order to refine that student's search further, every teacher would be interested in taking tuition first, then, their data should also be shown. If these facilities are implemented chiefly means, the number of mobile users will be increased. Therefore a teacher can register their name with professional data in order to offer a service to the students. The status record will be original and status is 'yes'.

B. Queries to select a mobile user to receive a service

The user has to search the available clients who are willing to provide a particular service. For any other applications, the user may become a client. In fig.1, end user terminal is shown. It depends upon mainly the client status, which is on or off conditions, category of service and environmental conditions such as locations, people's conduct [4].

Fig 1. End User terminal

The data model should contain relevant things closely to each other in order to avoid the duplication. The various assumptions made under this criteria, are more than enough to define a particular data into the particular application. There are more applications will be discussed in the upcoming chapter. The various category of end user services are shown in fig.2, the followings are most important. Vehicle pick up service, product pick up service, banking service, ticket booking service, emergency call service, sharing of personal interest to do something like tuition, advertisements, public services, guiding students in anyone of the subjects and also professional activities. If all users know when to call, where to call, then the communication will be taken between the users. Every user can show their identity to each other.

Fig 2. Category of End User services

III. CREATION OF DATA MODELS

A. Personal service

Location tracking using GPS is explained as an example for personal service. The data type is provided in the second column of the table 1., the main primary key is assumed as status, if the user want to share his location with others, the status value will be given as yes, or else no. Services will be offered only to allowed persons.

Column name	Data type
Mobile number	numeric(18,0)
Customer name	nchar(25)
Location	nchar(25)
GPS Locator	nchar(25)
Services required	nchar(25)
Availability(Permission restriction)	nchar(25)
User id	nchar(25)
Status	nchar(25)

Table 1. Personal service: example 1

Consider a user wants to share his location with family members, the data can be transferred to the particular family members while searching the location. In this table, the database contains information about food pickup services, banking services and ticket booking services.

For the mobile user who needs a food pickup service, refer table 2, that customer or mobile user has to register in the database as follows; Services required = food pickup, availability = order. Other data are as per the requirement. For the mobile user who can offer the food pick up service, that mobile user has to register in the database as follows: Services required = food pickup, availability = offer.

Column name	Data type
Mobile number	numeric(18,0)
Customer name	nchar(25)
Address	nchar(25)
Location	nchar(25)
Services required	nchar(25)
Availability	nchar(25)
User id	nchar(25)
Status	nchar(25)
Date& time	datetime

Table 2. Personal service: example 2

The query statements will be implemented as follows;

Select * from table name where Services required = food pickup, location = user choice, status =yes, datetime = user choice. Once a customer gets job finished, it is necessary to change the status to 'no' so that other customer can view only the available service and requirements.

B. Public service

In this table, Profession and location are the primary keys, a user wants to make a familiar company with all the mobile user, in any particular location, if the customer wants to know about the particular services which are offered by some particular persons such as doctors, lawyers.

Column name	Data type
Mobile number	numeric(18,0)
Customer name	nchar(25)
Address	nchar(25)
Profession	nchar(25)
Services required	nchar(25)
Services offered	nchar(25)
User id	nchar(25)
Status	nchar(25)
ID Card	nchar(25)

Table 3. Public service: example 1

The search option refines based on the profession and location, if the status is yes, unless stated otherwise. Doctors,

Lawyers can utilize this application to get familiar with other mobile users.

C. Private organizations

In this table, the database contains information about the private organizations. The services required column is a primary key and customer name and address will also be selected as secondary primary key. It may be banking service, or ticket booking service, an authorized person from respective bank or from office will come and finish the customer requirement in offline mode. ^[5] The services may be expanded after getting feedback from customers through various fields such as RFID technique, GPS locator and IMEI configurations.

Column name	Data type
Mobile number	numeric(18,0)
Organisation name	nchar(25)
Division or branch	nchar(25)
Address	nchar(25)
Location	nchar(25)
Services required	nchar(25)
Availability	nchar(25)
User id	nchar(25)
Status	nchar(25)
ID Card	nchar(25)

Table 4. Private Service: example 1

^[6] Detective agencies, vigilance offices and organizations can utilize this application mostly. Customer service for all electronic products is expected as valuable one. Using this application, a user can track that device, if that particular device ID is being used anywhere else. Police department can utilize this application for finishing the case file quickly and also search the unidentified materials quickly.

In this paper, there are two examples will be discussed. One is 'pickup service' and the other one is 'organization service'. A customer wants to give 'pickup service' from one point to any other point. This will be elaborately discussed in later chapter. All the professional peoples can have their identity with these services. If a customer wants to know a gynecologist doctor in any specified location, that customer can search profession, division and location. A lawyer can have same addressing technics accordingly to their affinity. An engineer can have based on his service nature. Likewise, also any shop owner can have their own location and contact number in these information pool region. Public data collection work can also be done using this application. For example, panchayat president, councilors, municipality chairman can be addressed by this application in an emergency situation.

IV. CREATING WINDOWS FORM APPLICATION USING C# IN VISUAL STUDIO

A). An application in an university campus:

In a college, there are lot of issues regarding with the communication between faculties, students, parents and management. Addressing all the peoples immediately is not possible in a hurry time. So, this application can be implemented. It comes under private category.

The database, this is the pool of information about the users. Every user has to get a login id, every user can address themselves in number of ways, for example, a parent can address him as father, this person can have more than one address like as an employee in a working place, like a member in some other public category, same as in the personal category also.

While getting admission, parents have to register in that application. After selecting the batch, department and stu name, the father details will be shown if its status is yes. This should be 'yes' compulsory, because its not personal category, it comes under private category.

Column name	Data type
fmnumber	numeric(18,0)
fname	nchar(25)
flocation	nchar(25)
stuname	nchar(25)
smnumber	numeric(18,0)
headmnumber	numeric(18,0)
ctmnumber	numeric(18,0)
fstatus	nchar(25)

Table 5. Table name: Studatabase

```
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.ComponentModel;
using System.Data;
using System.Drawing;
using System.Linq;
using System.Text;
using System.Threading.Tasks;
using System.Windows.Forms;
using System.Data.SqlClient;

namespace mytesttwo
{
    public partial class Form1 : Form
    {
        public Form1()
        {
            InitializeComponent();
        }
    }
}
```

```
private void button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    SqlConnection con = new
SqlConnection("Data Source=SAMYONE-
PC\\TEW_SQLSERVER;Initial
Catalog=universityone;Integrated
Security=True");
    con.Open();
    SqlCommand sc = new
SqlCommand("insert into studatabase values(" +
textBox1.Text + "," + textBox2.Text + "," +
textBox3.Text + "," + textBox4.Text + "," +
textBox5.Text + "," + textBox6.Text + "," +
textBox7.Text + "," + textBox8.Text + "');" ,
con);

    int O = sc.ExecuteNonQuery();
    MessageBox.Show(O + ": RECORD HAS
BEEN INSERTED");
    con.Close();
}

public static void main(string[] args)
{
    Application.Run(new Form1());
}

private void button2_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    Application.Exit();
}

private void button3_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    SqlConnection conn = new SqlConnection("Data
Source=SAMYONE-PC\\TEW_SQLSERVER;Initial
Catalog=universityone;Integrated
Security=True");
    SqlConnection connA = new
SqlConnection("Data Source=SAMYONE-
PC\\TEW_SQLSERVER;Initial
Catalog=universityone;Integrated
Security=True");
    SqlConnection connB = new
SqlConnection("Data Source=SAMYONE-
PC\\TEW_SQLSERVER;Initial
Catalog=universityone;Integrated
Security=True");
    SqlConnection connC = new
SqlConnection("Data Source=SAMYONE-
PC\\TEW_SQLSERVER;Initial
Catalog=universityone;Integrated
Security=True");
    SqlCommand command = new
SqlCommand(" SELECT fmnumber from studatabase
where stuname= '" + textBox4.Text + "'", conn);
    SqlCommand commandA = new
SqlCommand(" SELECT ctmnumber from studatabase
where stuname= '" + textBox4.Text + "'", connA);
}
```


Fig. 3. Student's data in university: Output window

Click ADD button. The conformation message will be displayed. Then enter 'stuname', click show button, the details will displayed in the list box accordingly. Then click 'nextapp', the second application is now ready to be executed. Here the primary key is 'stuname'.

B) An application of personal pick up service:

A mobile user can either offer a pickup service or order a pickup service. The following table is designed in SQL Server Management Studio 2012. And the code is executed in MS Visual Studio 2012 Express on c# platform. Here the primary key is 'FROMHERE'.

Column name	Data type
SEVICEREG	nchar(25)
PICKUPBY	nchar(25)
FROMHERE	nchar(25)
TOWARDS	nchar(25)
LANDMARK	nchar(25)
Clientbumber	numeric(18,0)
DAY	datetime

Table 6. Table name: perservice

```
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.ComponentModel;
using System.Data;
using System.Drawing;
using System.Linq;
using System.Text;
```

```
using System.Threading.Tasks;
using System.Windows.Forms;
using System.Data.SqlClient;
namespace mytesttwo
{
    public partial class Form2 : Form
    {
        public Form2()
        {
            InitializeComponent();
        }

        private void button3_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {
            Application.Exit();
        }

        private void button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {
            SqlConnection con = new
            SqlConnection("Data Source=SAMYONE-
            PC\\TEW_SQLEXPRESS;Initial
            Catalog=universityone;Integrated
            Security=True");
            con.Open();
            SqlCommand sc = new
            SqlCommand("insert into perservice values(' +
            textBox1.Text + "',' + textBox2.Text + "',' +
            textBox3.Text + "',' + textBox4.Text + "',' +
            textBox5.Text + "',' + textBox6.Text + "',' +
            textBox7.Text + '');" , con);
            int 0 = sc.ExecuteNonQuery();
            MessageBox.Show(0 + ": RECORD HAS
            BEEN INSERTED");
            con.Close();
        }

        public static void main(string[] args)
        {
            Application.Run(new Form2());
        }

        private void button4_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {
            textBox5.Text = " ";
            textBox6.Text = " ";
            textBox7.Text = " ";
            textBox1.Text = " ";
            textBox2.Text = " ";
            textBox3.Text = " ";
            textBox4.Text = " ";
            listBox1.Items.Clear();
            listBox2.Items.Clear();
            listBox3.Items.Clear();
            listBox4.Items.Clear();
            listBox5.Items.Clear();
            listBox6.Items.Clear();
        }
    }
}
```

```

    }
    private void button2_Click(object
sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        SqlConnection conn = new
SqlConnection("Data Source=SAMYONE-
PC\\TEW_SQLEXPRESS;Initial
Catalog=universityone;Integrated
Security=True");

        SqlCommand command = new
SqlCommand(" SELECT SEVICEREG, clientnumber,
TOWARDS, LANDMARK, DAY, PICKUPBY from perservice
where FROMHERE = '" + textBox3.Text + "'",
conn);

        try
        {
            conn.Open();
            SqlDataReader reader
= command.ExecuteReader();

            while (reader.Read())
            {

listBox1.Items.Add(reader["clientnumber"].ToStri
ng());

listBox2.Items.Add(reader["SEVICEREG"].ToString(
));

listBox3.Items.Add(reader["TOWARDS"].ToString())
;

listBox4.Items.Add(reader["LANDMARK"].ToString())
;

listBox5.Items.Add(reader["DAY"].ToString());

listBox6.Items.Add(reader["PICKUPBY"].ToString())
;

            }
            reader.Close();
        }
        catch (SqlException ex)
        {
            MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
        }
        finally
        {
            conn.Close();
            {
            }
        }
    }
}
}

```

The output window:

Fig.4. Pick-up service: Output window

IV. FUTURE SCOPE

The peoples are identified by their characters, professions, relationships, names and particulaly services. The need of the mobile number will become the second option, while peoples are searching the services first. This application will be helpful in the design of various ‘Internet of things’ models in future. This application makes the peoples to think good in all aspects, because it can act as a bridge between the mobile users, even the mobile number is not known by the end users. It can be implemented widely where a particular group of peoples working together based on their relationship and services. after getting feedback from users, and upon the recommendation , it can be superstructured with multi-dimensions among the mobile users. In high end versions, it will be availabe with the online forms by which user can create and share the mobile numbers within a group of peoples. For example, consider a particular organisation is going to conduct a conference, usually the brochure will be prepared to notice this to all the peoples. After registration, using this application, the participants may able to get all the participant’s mobile number to communicate with each others.

The database will be created to the participants where participants can either enter their mobile number or addresses or can get the same. This application will be helpful to the organiser to manage the database which is operated by online form. As primary key will be the 'location of the conference' or 'conference name', all the participants can either enter their details into the database or can retrieve details from database. The security and data details with all the safety measures will be controlled in internet server.

In detective and forensic services, a user can upload a document or data into this application, such as vehicle number, mobile IMEI number, location tracking of the individual, movement tracking to the personal members can also be done with the help of other mobile user. The product should be valid until the original user uses his package. The network service provider can track the IMEI when the FIR is filed from the customer. If this particular application is connected with IMEI number, the information about this mobile readily available to that customer. This application will be used in these type of detective services also.

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